

Polynomial equations over bijective dynamical systems and their semiring extensions

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A very general way to formalise finite deterministic processes is as *finite discrete dynamical systems* (FDDSs), i.e., as iterated transition functions $f: A \rightarrow A$ over finite sets A of states or, equivalently, as functional (uniform outdegree 1) digraphs. All concrete, succinctly described finite models, such as automata networks and their restrictions (e.g., finite cellular automata and reaction systems) can be easily expressed this way, and all complexity lower bounds on FDDSs represented explicitly immediately apply to them as well.

When the exact nature of the states is immaterial (e.g., in engineering applications with specifications having multiple possible implementations) or unknown (e.g., in scientific observations with instruments accurate enough to distinguish different states but not to analyse them), we can push this abstraction one step further and take FDDSs *up to isomorphism*, as we will do in the following.

A fundamental question when dealing with an FDDS (A, f) up to isomorphism is whether it consists, in fact, of multiple independent FDDSs in synchronous execution. This corresponds to asking whether (A, f) can be factored into nontrivial (A_1, f_1) and (A_2, f_2) with respect to the *direct* (a.k.a. Kronecker or categorical) *product* of digraphs, that is, if $(A, f) = (A_1 \times A_2, f_1 \times f_2)$ where $(f_1, f_2)(x) = (f_1(x), f_2(x))$. The dual operation, which must be inevitably taken into account as the product of connected FDDSs can be disconnected, is the disjoint union (a.k.a. Kronecker or categorical sum) of digraphs, defined as $(A_1, f_1) + (A_2, f_2) = (A_1 \sqcup A_2, f_1 + f_2)$ with $(f_1 + f_2)(x) = f_i(x)$ iff $x \in A_i$.

The algebraic structure $(\mathbb{D}, +, \times)$ of FDDSs up to isomorphism is a commutative semiring (i.e., a ring without subtraction), with 0 being the empty FDDS and 1 a fixed point [2]. This semiring contains an isomorphic copy of \mathbb{N} , the FDDS with n fixed points playing the role of n , and is in general quite complex algebraically, in particular lacking unique factorisations into irreducibles. Like any other semiring, \mathbb{D} comes with its associated semirings of k -variate polynomials $\mathbb{D}[\vec{X}]$, which allow us to formulate many FDDS decomposition problems in terms of equations, with varying computability and complexity as a function of the classes of polynomials allowed on both sides of the equations:

Problem. Is the k -variate polynomial equation $P(\vec{X}) = Q(\vec{X})$ solvable in \mathbb{D}^k ?

If P and Q are unrestricted, this is undecidable by reduction from Hilbert's tenth problem over the naturals, while the problem is decidable in **NP** if Q is constant [2]. Some further (rather strong) restrictions, such as P being univariate and injective, make the problem tractable (see [1,3,4] and the references therein).

In this work we focus on the subsemiring of permutations or bijections $\mathbb{P} \subseteq \mathbb{D}$, whose elements are sums of cycles, and on the semiring extensions $\mathbb{N} \subseteq \mathbb{N}[\mathcal{C}] \subseteq \mathbb{P}$,

where $\mathbb{N}[\mathcal{C}]$ is obtained by adjoining a *finite* set \mathcal{C} of cycles to \mathbb{N} and closing under sums and products¹. Since powers of a cycle are multiples of the cycle itself, these semiring extensions (unlike, e.g., those obtained by adjunction of non-bijective FDDSs) enjoy the nice algebraic property of having finite degree (dimension) over \mathbb{N} , even if it is generally exponential w.r.t. the size of \mathcal{C} :

Lemma. *Any element of $\mathbb{N}[\mathcal{C}]$ is a unique linear combination over \mathbb{N} of the cycles obtained from all products of subsets of \mathcal{C} .*

Furthermore, one never needs to look too far in order to establish solvability:

Lemma. *A k -variate polynomial equation $P(\vec{X}) = Q(\vec{X})$ with coefficients in $\mathbb{N}[\mathcal{C}]$ is solvable in \mathbb{D}^k if and only if it is in $\mathbb{N}[\mathcal{D}]^k$, where \mathcal{D} is \mathcal{C} closed under divisors.*

These results, together with a reduction from MONOTONE-3SAT, first to a system of linear equations over \mathbb{P} (with an encoding of all Boolean variables into just two FDDSs), then to their linear combination in a larger semiring, allow us to obtain both lower and upper complexity (and computability) bounds:

Theorem. *Linear equations over \mathbb{P} , and thus over \mathbb{D} , are **NP-hard** even with a constant side and just three variables.*

Theorem. *Multivariate linear equations over \mathbb{P} are decidable in **NEXPTIME**, and in **NP** if the semiring of their coefficients has polynomial degree over \mathbb{N} .*

Beside tightening these complexity bounds, several interesting open problems remain: for instance, finding the minimum number of variables that makes linear equations intractable, the complexity of establishing irreducibility, and whether quadratic and cubic equations are decidable over \mathbb{D} and \mathbb{P} (this is, respectively, decidable and unknown over \mathbb{N}), in particular with a small, constant number of variables. Are finite dynamical systems strictly tougher than natural numbers?

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¹ See also [1] for a similar approach, but with *infinite* cycles of prime power lengths.